

Analysis For Financial Management Regulations As Medi-Ation The Effect Between Human Resources Development On The Performance Of Regional Government Financial Management

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 05, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 08, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Financial Management Regulations, Human Resource Development, Performance On Local Government Financial Management</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6015314</p>	<p><i>The performance of local government financial management is a success on local governments in managing their finances in an orderly, regulatory, efficient, effective, economical, and transparent manner. Achievement for optimal financial management performance is influenced by human resource development and understanding for financial management regulations. In this study, we investigated the mediating effect between a local government financial management regulations. The survey was conducted with saturated sampling of 148 leaders of regional apparatus organizations (OPD) in Timor, the Province of NTT-Indonesia, but only 138 people could be identified. The SEM-PLS analysis results shown that the direct effect between human resource development and local government financial management performance is not significant. There is understanding of regional financial management regulations has a significant positive effect on the performance of local government financial management. Human resource development has a significant positive effect on understanding of regional financial management regulations. The results analysis shown that there is a role of full mediation from the variable understanding on financial management regulations for the human resource development variable with the performance of local government financial management. We describe further discussions and implications in this paper.</i></p>

Introduction

Regional government financial management is an implementation of Law no. 22 of 1999 concerning regional autonomy and Law no. 25 of 1999 concerning the financial balance of the central government and local governments. Then, the guideline for local government financial management is Permendagri No. 21 of 2011 and Government Regulation no. 11 of 2008 concerning procedures for preparing development plans and budgets. Hopefully, the central government with any implementation of regional autonomy can provided by the widest possible opportunity for local governments to implement government systems, budget management, supervision, and optimal service for the people in their respective regions in Indonesia.

To achieve success in the process of local government financial management, human resources, in this case the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) must have the ability or expertise in accounting and regional financial management. To achieve success in the financial management of local governments, government institutions as public sector organizations in carrying out their duties as servants of the State and servants of the community, every civil servant must be professional and have good competence in terms of mastery of knowledge, expertise, morals, and good mentality (Gajewski, 2005; Carley, 1995). Human resource development can be carried out in several ways, including further education to a higher level than previous education, training and empowerment.

We noted that the government's attention to human resource development is considerable. As evidence of the government's concern for human resource development, in this case ASN, the issuance of Presidential Regulation No. 12 of 1961 and the Circular of the Minister of Empowerment of the State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia No. 04 of 2013 concerning the granting of study assignments and study permits for regional and central civil servants.

Interpreting institutional theory was rules that can be used as guidelines in limiting human actions and behavior, so there are no deviations in carrying out organizational activities (North, 1994; Yeager, 1999, Bickenbach, Frank, et al., 1999), and institutions can be said as a container that can reduce uncertainty in human interaction through the creation of behavior (Pejovich, 1995).

We noted that an institutional theory in research is carried out with a regulatory approach or regulations issued by the government with the intention of being able to serve as basic guidelines in the management of local government finances in Indonesia. An existence of this government regulation will limit the actions and behavior of ASNs that can directly or indirectly harm State finances.

In this study, we investigated that the effect between mediation on the proposed by hypothetical model. Our observation has been no research investigating the understanding of financial management regulations as a mediating variable, any variable of financial management regulations is used as the dependent variable.

THEORY AND HYPOTHESIS

Human Resources Development and local government financial management performance

The flow of human resource development theory argued about organizations that have high potential human resources do not guarantee, so they will be successful at work, but they must understand what must be done according to the provisions and not according to their own will (Dessler, 2010). Human resources owned by the organization must be developed through education, training, and based on work commitment. So, they can always have a sustainable impact on the organization (Skagg, et al., 2004). In the public organization sector, human resources have a significant influence on the performance of local government financial management according to research results from: Dev Raj Adhikari, 2009; Tehmina et al., 2005; Edelman et al., 2005; In addition to the research results, there is theoretical support from Skagg et al., 2004; Gajewski, 2005; Soni, 2004.

H1: Human resource development has a significant effect on the performance of local government financial management

Financial management regulations and local government financial management performance

A performance of local government financial management is the government's ability to optimize the use on a budget in an orderly, obedient, efficient, effective, and transparent manner (Mardiasmo, 2002) towards good governance. To achieve optimal financial performance, it was very important for every budget manager and user to understand the management regulations properly, so as to support the performance of government financial management optimally (Jackson, 1995b); (Jones, 1995).

Several previous studies explaining the effect of regulation on financial performance Ce'Cile et al., (2005), the results of their research shown that regulation has a significant effect on financial performance on the stock market in Canada. Likewise Ivan et al., (2011), the results are shown that the variables of regulation, awareness and compliance have a significant effect on financial performance. Norkholis et al., (2014) founded that the implementation of regulations has no significant effect on the performance of local government financial management.

H2: A financial management regulations has a significant effect on the performance of local government financial management

Human resources development and understanding of financial management regulations

An understanding of local financial management regulations is very appropriate for every individual entrusted by the local government in managing local government finances. Regulations can be achieved through education, training, seminars and empowerment for every local government budget management apparatus. Regulations on regional financial management include; (1) government regulation number 58 of 2005 concerning regional financial management, (2) ministerial regulation number 21 of 2011 concerning regional financial management guidelines, (3) regional government regulation number 11 of 2008 concerning the principles of regional financial management. The purpose of developing human resources through education, training, and empowerment an existing officials is intended. So, a budget users and managers can understand for existing regulations relating to local government financial management. With the development of human resources, every apparatus can be ascertained that they can understand well the financial management regulations properly, so there are no errors in their application (I Wayan, 2015). From these figures it can be said that human resource development has a significant effect on the level of understanding of local government financial management regulations.

H3: Human resource development has a significant effect on the understanding of local government financial management regulations

Human resource development and local government financial management performance are mediated by understanding financial management regulations

A development of human resources as the manager on the government budget has an indirect impact on the performance for a local government financial management if they do not properly understand the regulations that are related to regional financial management. Its implementation will be futile if it is not well understood by executives as budget users and managers. The purpose of developing human resources by the government through education and coaching as stipulated in government regulation Number 58 of 2005 article 130 and number 04 of 2013 concerning the provision of guidelines, guidance, supervision, consultation, education, training, research and development. This is intended that users and Regional financial managers in each OPD

can understand and apply the regulations referred to as guidelines that must be adhered to in managing local government finances (Devas, 1998).

The performance of local government financial management will be optimal if every budget user and manager understands well the regulations that have been established by the Indonesian government. In this research study, we set any variable understanding of financial management regulations as a mediating variable and this is what differentiates us from previous studies.

H4: Human resource development has a significant effect on the performance of local government financial management mediated by an understanding of regional financial management regulations.

Picture 1. Conceptual Framework

Source between variables:

1. Dev Raj Adhikari, (2009) Edelman et al., (2005); Tehmina et al., (2015)
2. Ce'Çile et al., (2005); Ivan et al., (2011)
3. I wayan, (2015)

METHODOLOGY

Types of research

To answer the research hypothesis as mentioned above, this type of research is explanatory in which, it will explain the variables of local government financial management performance based on explanatory variables, such as human resource development variables, regulations, and a local financial management mechanisms (Maholtra, 1999: 84).

Location and time of study

This research was carried out at local governments in Timor, East Nusa Tenggara Province - Indonesia, which took place from 27 February to 27 April 2017.

Research population

The population were all leaders of regional apparatus organizations (OPD) in the Regency and City Government in Timor, East Nusa Tenggara Province.

**Table 1. Number of Respondents in District and City Governments
In Timor, East Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia**

No	Regency/City	Total of OPD	Sample of OPD
1	Kupang City	29	29
2	Kupang Regency	30	30
3	TTS Regency	28	28
4	TTU Regency	30	30
5	Belu Regency	31	31
Total of Respondent			148

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2018

Sample

The method of determining a sample in this research is saturated sampling technique or population research (Sauders et al., 2009) in the local government in Timor, East Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia. Criteria for respondent is a leader of the regional apparatus organization (OPD) as the unit of analysis. There are 148

organizational leaders Regional apparatus (OPD) in the district and city governments in East Nusa Tenggara - Indonesia, but only 138 respondents could participate in this research.

Data analysis method

The research data analysis methods in our research are descriptive analysis and inferential statistical analysis, namely Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) - Partial Least Square (PLS) and using Smart PLS, Microsoft Excel, and SPSS Software, to test hypotheses and produce a viable model (fit), and qualitative analysis, such to strengthen the findings in order to gain a deep understanding on a phenomena that exist in the field.

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis in research is intended to be able to interpret the perceptions of each respondent towards the research question through a questionnaire distributed during the research. An instrument is a questionnaire using the Likert scale, which is used to measure respondents' attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of the object (Nazir, 2009). The determination of the Likert scale in this study starts from a scale of 1 to 5 for all variables. The scale range used is numbers 1 to 5. Raise 1 indicated that a strongly disagree / conform, number 2 indicates disagree / appropriate, number 3 indicates quite agree / conform, number 4 indicates agree / conform, number 5 indicates strongly agree / conform (Maholtra, 2010, Cooper & Sehinder, 2003: 299).

Partial Least Square (PLS) Analysis

Testing for a hypothesis in this study we used SEM-PLS on the grounds that it has been widely applied in management research (Heir et al., 2012). Partial Least Square (PLS) is a powerful analytical method because it can be applied to all data scales, in analysis. Partial Least Square (PLS) also does not require many assumptions and the sample size does not have to be large in number, besides that it can also be analyzed at the same time the constructs formed by reflective and formative indicators. Testing for a mediation variables is carried out by using the Sobel Test. Mediating variable analysis is used as a method for examining an indirect effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables in the study through the coefficient in indirect relationship. A method of examining the mediating variables refers to a theory put forward by Baron and Kenny (1986) that determines whether or not a direct or indirect relationship exists. For the calculation process, the online Sobel test is used at <http://quantpsy.org/sobel/sobel.htm>, where the independent variable is denoted by X, the dependent variable is denoted by Y, and the mediating variable is denoted by Z.

The structural model in the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach is the relationship between latent variables called the inner model, while any measurement model of each indicator, both flexible and formative, is called the outer model. The inner model can be evaluated by looking at the percentage value of variance described, such by looking at the R² (R-square exogenous variable) value for the dependent variable construct using the Stone-Geiser Q-Square test measure and seeing the coefficient of the structural path. Any stability of this estimate was evaluated using the t-statistical test obtained through the bootstrapping procedure (Ghozali, 2006). Furthermore, convergent validity for the reflective model, any correlation between the item score / component score with the construct score becomes the basis for assessing the indicator. Reflective standard measurement is said to be high, if the correlation value exceeds 0.70 with the construct to be measured. However, for research that is still in the exploratory category or in the early stages of development, for the standard measurement scale it can be a loading value of only 0.50 or 0.60 (Chin, 1998 in Ghozali, 2006), the value of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is suggested, so exceeding or greater than 0.50 at the 95% confidence level or $\alpha = 0.05$ (Fornell and Larcker, 1981 in Ghozali, 2006).

Qualitative information analysis

The purpose of qualitative information analysis is to get a deep picture of a particular problem / phenomenon through an inductive thought process. From this approach the researcher is involved intensively in interacting with key informants who represent all respondents, by focusing on the performance of local government financial management.

RESULT

Table 2. Characteristics of Research Respondents

Respondent Characteristics		Frequency (org)	Percentage (%)
Gender	a.Man	124	89.86
	b. Women	14	10.14
Total		138	100

Education	Undergraduate	89	64.49
	Postgraduate	49	35.51
	Total	138	100
Position Category	Category IV	138	100

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2018

Measurement Model

The results of data analysis using SEM-PLS resulted in two types of analysis results, such as measurement model and structural model. The first thing we do is estimate a validity and reliability of each construct and indicator of this study. For all the research indicators as in table 4 shown that all indicators have an outer loading value above 0.60, an alpha value above 0.70 indicated that all constructs have a sufficient level of internal consistency (Gefen et al., 2000). AVE above 0.5 indicated that the research instrument is said to be convergent valid (Roldan, Sanchez-Franco, 2012).

Table 3. Evaluation Results of the Measurement Model

Variable	Variable	Variable	Variable	Variable	Variable	Variable
Human Resource Management (X1)	Education (X1.1)	X1.1.1	0.755	0.887	0.850	0.568
		X1.1.2	0.811			
	Training (x1.2)	X1.2.1	0.645			
		X1.2.2	0,694			
	Empowerment (X1.3)	X1.3.1	0.826			
		X1.3.2	0.774			
Financial Management Regulations (Z1)	Work Plan and Budget	Z1.1	0.774	0.864	0.806	0.621
	Budget Realization	Z1.2	0.769			
	Administration System	Z1.3	0.739			
	Control, supervision, evaluation	Z1.4	0.830			
	Regent / Mayor Regulation	Z1.5	0.794			
Local Government Financial Management Performance (Y1)	Orderly	Y1.1	0.758	0.908	0.878	0.622
	Obedience	Y1.2	0.795			
	Effective	Y1.3	0.778			
	Efficient	Y1.4	0.801			
	Economical	Y1.5	0.784			
	Transparant	Y1.6	0.811			

Source: Data Processed Research, 2018

Structural Model

In the structural model in this study, we tested the proposed hypothesis with bootstrapping procedure and the algorithm (attached) to shown any results for each pathway in the model as shown in Table 3 about significant relationship was found in the effect between financial management regulations and performance. For a local government financial management ($\beta = 0.374$, $\rho < 0.00$, t-statistic value $3.388 > t\text{-table } 1.960$) and the effect between human resource development on financial management regulations ($\beta = 0.353$, $\rho < 0.005$, t-statistic value $2.793 > t\text{-table } 1.960$). Thus, hypothesis 2 and 3 are accepted, so an insignificant relationship was founded on the effect between human resource development and the performance of local government financial management ($\beta = 0.102$, $\rho < 0.031$, t-statistic value $0.854 < t\text{-table } 1.960$)

Table 4. Results of the Structural Model Evaluation

Hypothesis	The relationship between variables	Coefficient	T-statistic	p-value	Results
H1	Human resource development with performance management of local government finances	0.102(Ns)	0.854	0.031	Rejected
H2	Regulations with the performance of local government financial management	0.374*	3.448	0.001	Accepted
H3	Human resources development with a financial management regulations	0.353*	2.793	0.005	Accepted

Noted: * Significant $p < 0.05$; Ns = non significant; t-statistic > 1.960 (Two-tailed test); n=Sample=138

The Effects of Mediation

We conducted a mediation test using online test Sobel referring to the test of Baron and Kenny (1986) that determines whether or not there is a direct or indirect relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable at <http://quantpsy.org/sobel/sobel.htm>, where the independent variable is denoted by X, the dependent variable is denoted by Y, and the mediating variable is denoted by Z. The Sobel test is related to testing the significance level of the path coefficient of indirect influence. In this study we used the real level $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table 5. Calculation by the online Sobel test

Input:	Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a 0.353	Sobel test: 2.18604644	0.06039304	0.02881221
b 0.374	Aroian test: 2.13353049	0.06187959	0.03288123
s _a 0.126	Goodman test: 2.24264163	0.05886897	0.02491993
s _b 0.107	Reset all	Calculate	

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2018

Our results proven that the direct relationship is not significant between human resource development and local government financial management performance as a first step for this test (c); $\beta = 0.102$; $p < 0.05$; t-statistic = 0.854 $<$ t-table 1.960. The results of testing the relationship between human resource development and a regional financial management regulations were found to be significant (a); $\beta = 0.353$; $p < 0.05$; t-statistic = 2.793 $>$ t-table = 1.960. Thus, some results are shown that the relationship between regional financial management regulations and the performance of local government financial management are found to be significant (b); $\beta = 0.374$; $p < 0.05$; t-statistic = 3.488 $>$ t-table = 1.960. As a comparison with the results of the direct effect test in Table 5, human resource development has no significant effect on the

performance of local government financial management ($\beta = 0.102$, Ns) but, after including the mediation variable as a mediator it has a significant effect ($\beta = 0.209$; $p < 0.05$; $t\text{-statistic} = 2.186 < t\text{-table} = 1.960$, means that the results of this test proved that the financial management regulations can act as a full mediation (Baron & Kenny, 1986).

DISCUSSION

Empirically, there is sufficient evidence that human resource development has an insignificant positive effect on the performance of local government financial management. This finding does not support previous research (Edelman et al., (2005); Dev Raj A (2009); Tehmina et al., (2015). The philosophy of local government financial management performance is a regional financial administration management can be carried out in an orderly manner, obeying the regulations that is applicable, efficient, effective, economical, and transparent in regional financial management. Human resource development has been carried out through; education to a higher level, training and empowerment, but it has not contributed significantly to improving the performance of local government financial management in Timor, Nusa Southeast East-Indonesia. Likewise, it is also empirically proven that the understanding of regional financial management regulations has a significant effect on the performance of local government financial management. This finding supports previous studies (Ce'Cile et al., (2005); Ivan et al., (2011) with the findings of previous research Nurkholis et al., (2014).

Empirical evidence is proven that human resource development has a significant positive effect on the understanding of regional financial management regulations. We find that the understanding of regional financial management regulations can act as a full mediator between human resource development and the performance of local government financial management, this means that to achieve the maximum performance of local government financial management, the managers and users of local government budgets must understand well and correctly about regional financial management regulations.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

This study did not include financial staff at each OPD, so the results were not able to provide a complete picture of the performance of local government financial management in Timor, East Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia. The results also can only be applied to government agencies and are not relevant if applied to non-governmental organizations. The results for empirical analysis are only based on survey data which provides analysis of the relationship at one point in time (cross sectional), while the public or community environment is constantly changing. This study has not identified these changes.

There are still other variables that affect to the performance of local government financial management that have not been included in this study, such as variables of organizational behavior, organizational culture, work motivation as independent / exogenous variables. Guidelines for local government financial management that are used are the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 21 of 2011, but in the accountability of regional financial management there are still local governments that are guided by the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 13 of 2006. Likewise, the government accounting system still refers to the accounting system cash based.

CONCLUSION

The results of our research provide empirical evidenced that human resource development does not directly contribute positively to the performance of local government financial management in East Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia and this is contrary to the theoretical basis of human resources. For this reason, it can be said that human resource development what has been done now needs to be addressed in the future. Additionally, regional financial management regulations has a positive impact on the performance of local government financial management. It was founded that the understanding of financial management regulations has been applied properly and correctly in the process of local government financial administration management.

Human resource development in the field of financial management has a positive impact on budget managers and users in understanding regional financial management regulations. A financial management regulations was found to be able to mediate the relationship between human resource development and local government financial management performance. We hope that future research can add to human resource development indicators, such as work experience, work commitment. Likewise, it can also examine other variables that are considered to have influenced to the performance of local government financial administration management such as organizational behavior, organizational culture, and work motivation in order to obtain a general picture of the things that affect to the performance of local government financial administration management.

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